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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D7.2 Italian River Pilot Solutions description, test results and impact assessment.

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AE	Acoustic Emission System
AGN	Agreement on Main Inland Waterways of International importance
AIPo	Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po
ARSTPC	Agenzia per la sicurezza territoriale e la protezione civile (Emilia-Romagna)
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CI	Cold Ironing
CNC	Core Network Corridors of TEN-T
DT	Digital Twin
EnoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EU	European Union
FBG	Fiber Bragg Grating sensors
FEWS	Flood Early Warning System
FOS	Fiber Optic Sensor Technology
GA	Grant Agreement
IV	Infrastrutture Venete S.r.l.
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
IWW	Inland Waterway
KET	Key enabling technologies
KPI	Key performance indicator
LL	Living Labs
MIT	Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport
ML	Machine Learning

NST	Standard goods classification for transport statistics
RIS	River Information Services
SB	Smart Bulletin
SCMS	Synchro-modal Corridor Management System
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UN	United Nations
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

The report aims to describe the results of the tests on the technologies applied in the Italian pilot on the Po River. In detail, we can distinguish some technologies developed in the CRISTAL project (Fiber Optic Sensors, led by ENEA, SCMS, and Acoustic emissions, led by CERTH, Digital Twin led by Fraunhofer) and the specific solutions of the Italian pilot (Forecasting model of navigability conditions and Smart Bulletin, led by AIPO, Feasibility study for cold iron solutions, led by IV, Infrastrutture Venete).

The premises and context in which the tests are carried out have been defined in deliverable D7.1. That report underlines the differences between the different routes that make up the Italian river infrastructures and identifies the objectives to which the CRISTAL project is tending, namely, to make river navigation more modern, sustainable, and able to integrate with other modes of transport of goods and passengers.

This report describes in more detail the methods of application of the solutions identified, the technical characteristics, the functionalities, and the innovations compared to the state of the art.

Particularly important in the context of the Italian pilot are the governance models of waterways, where the lack of clear rules and tools to support companies is very much felt by the operators. To understand and highlight these needs, two tools have been developed as part of the CRISTAL project: the Manifesto for the sustainable development of the Padano-Veneto waterway system and the gap analysis that analyses the organisation of the main operators in this sector and the public entities that have the task of infrastructure management and planning.

The report is completed with an evaluation of the impact of the solutions adopted with respect to the objectives of the CRISTAL project.

1.1. Introduction

The main goal of the D7.2 is to provide an overview of the tests run in the Italian pilot.

Italian River Pilot has three main objectives: to increase the reliability of IWW, to improve its sustainability, and finally to make the preventive maintenance of locks and the riverbed more effective. All the objectives are linked to the CRISTAL global objectives, which are to improve the reliability of IWW transportation and increase its share in the different transport modes.

An important leverage in achieving these objectives is given by digitization, which can be applied both to develop tools for monitoring the conditions of the riverbed to ensure safe navigation and to provide companies with tools to promote the better organisation of their business. In the first case, the reference solutions are the digital twin and the use of tools that use acoustic emissions to assess the state of the infrastructure, the FOS, which allows the depth of the seabed to be monitored through the measurement of debris. In the second case, the SCMS and the smart bullet offer operators management tools that facilitate the operation and scheduling of loads and trips.

In Italy, inland navigation accounts for less than 1% of the total goods handled. A share very far from those achieved in other countries such as France, Germany and the Netherlands. This implies that the sector needs a strong development not only of technology but also of rules, for internal regulation and to promote

integration with other modes of transport and reduce the imbalance that currently penalizes inland navigation operators compared to those in the maritime sector.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

This section provides an overview of the alignment of the document to the formal deliverable & corresponding task descriptions included in the GA and thus help the deliverable owners and the reviewers to conclude on the level of achievement of the deliverable/task goals.

Table 1 Alignment of D7.2 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D7.2 Po River Pilot solutions description, test results and impact assessment	<i>Aim of the pilot</i>	<i>Chapter 2 Aim of the pilot</i>	<i>The chapter 2 briefly illustrates the aim of the Italian pilot</i>
	<i>Results of the pilot</i>	<i>Chapters 3, 4</i>	<i>Chapter 3 collects the results of the technology development and testing carried out by the partners involved in the Italian pilot</i> <i>Chapter 4 offers a summary description of the main output of the Living Labs carried out with the Italian inland navigation stakeholders</i>
	<i>Impact assessment</i>	<i>Chapter 5</i>	<i>Chapter 5 focuses on the impact of CRISTAL on inland navigation</i>
TASKS			
Task 7.1 Pilot supervision, concept assessment and coordination with WP6	<i>On the basis of the scenario set in WP1, the solutions proposed by WP2, WP3, WP5 and the input from WP6, the set of technologies and system to be tested in the Po River pilot will be</i>	<i>Chapters 1-6</i>	<i>Based on the premises and assessment made in D71, this chapter describes the technologies applied to the Italian pilot project and the results of the tests conducted both in</i>

	<i>identified with the related monitoring technique and KPI.</i>		<i>laboratory and along the riverbed.</i>
Task 7.2 Engineering and implementation: New forecasting navigability model and green port cold ironing	<p><i>This task is addressing:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• The realisation of a prediction model for Po river navigability conditions</i> <i>• The study for the realization of a network of cold ironing facilities along the Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante e Po – Brondolo channel including a dedicated designing model guidelines and a related masterplan for the implementation</i> 	<i>Paragraphs 3.5, 3.6</i>	<p><i>Description of objectives and test results of the navigability prediction model</i></p> <p><i>Feasibility study on cold ironing along the Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante e Po – Brondolo channel</i></p>
Task 7.3 Corridor management & organisational models for sustainability, resilience and competitiveness of the territorial synchromodal transport system	<p><i>This task will implement different applications of WP3 Corridor management:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• A new smart daily report navigability conditions.</i> 	<i>Paragraphs 3.4, 3.5</i>	<p><i>Description of the design and of the functionalities of SCMS</i></p> <p><i>Model of the Smart Bulletin</i></p>
Task 7.4 Governance: Living labs activation and management	<i>Setting up a sustainable stakeholder’s partnership for longer term collaboration through the living lab concept in order to develop a resilient, more competitive and more entrepreneurial regional inland waterways transport and logistic economy.</i>	<i>Chapter 4</i>	<i>Manifesto Gap Analysis</i>

Task 7.5 Digital twin		<i>Paragraph 3.3</i>	<i>Description of main objective and test results of DT in Italian Po River Pilot</i>
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1.3. Deliverable overview and report structure

The report aims to describe the results of the tests on the technologies applied in the Italian pilot on the Po River.

The present report is divided into two main sections:

Section 1 (chapters 2, 3 and 4): chapter 2 summarises the context and objectives of the Italian pilot. Chapter 3 describes the objectives of the technologies, and the methodologies applied for experimentation and the results of the tests. Two groups of applications can be distinguished: the first group is formed by the technologies developed within the CRISTAL project, namely FOS (ENEA), Acoustic Emissions (CERTH), Digital Twin (Fraunhofer) and SCMS (CERTH); the second group includes the specific applications of the Italian pilot, i.e. Navigability Prediction Model and Smart Bulletin (AIPO), a feasibility study of cold Ironing (Infrastrutture Venete). Chapter 4 describes the outputs of the Living Labs, in particular the Manifesto for the sustainable development of the Padano-Veneto inland waterway system. Although it is not a product of the Living Labs, the Gap analysis was possible thanks to the engagement of stakeholders during the Living Labs.

Section 2: (chapters 5, 6): in chapter 5 an evaluation of the impact of the technologies tested in the Italian pilot and the KPIs calculated for some applications is made. Chapter 6 contains some conclusions.

2. Aim of the pilot

This chapter summarises the description of the Po River-Veneto waterway system and the objectives of the WP7 Po River Pilot.

2.1. Pilot schedule and assumptions

The Italian pilot of the CRISTAL project is composed of the Po River and the Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante – Po Brondolo waterway. These waterways connect the port of Mantua with the Adriatic Sea and the Venetian Lagoon, crossing one of the most economically active parts of Northern Italy (Figure 1).

More details on the physical characteristics, traffic flows and main operators of these waterways are contained in the Deliverable “D7.1 RP specification and Baseline measurements of the WP7 Italian River Pilot”.

Figure 1 The Padano -Veneto water way system

Source: Deliverable D7.1

In line with the Grant Agreement of the CRISTAL project, the general objectives of the Italian River Pilot are:

1. *Improvement of the assets management of the inland waterways infrastructure, taking into account the new digital technologies (including the digital twin), biodiversity and environmental impacts, green energy procurement, the resilience certification, the COPERNICUS climate services, the climate model and the interoperable support decision system supplied by the Critical Infrastructure Research and Resilience Network–CIPCast.*
2. *Testing innovative technology for medium term forecast of the navigability condition and studying the implementation of cold-ironing facilities along the quays.*

3. Innovation and improvement of the governance process of the “River Po Corridor management”, supporting for route planning, voyage planning, transport and traffic management, securing (contingency management) the supply for goods for the relevant supply chain and for tourism management, aiming to (WP3, WP4, WP5).
4. Digitalization of the logistic and of the people transport services (multimodality and a synchro modality perspective).
5. Reduction of the CO2-Footprint of the river management services and support of the „Business continuity management“ of the transport services.

To achieve these goals, the working group has developed and tested various technologies, decision support tools and governance models (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Italian Pilot tools and innovative solutions

Source: Deliverable D7.1

3. Po River pilot solutions description and test results

This chapter describes the technologies applied to the Italian pilot project and the results of the tests conducted in the Po River context. The sequence of paragraphs begins with the technologies tested within the CRISTAL project and across the three pilot cases. Subsequently, the technologies and systems specific to the Italian pilot are illustrated.

For the sake of completeness of the technologies/solutions developed on the initiative of the Italian pilot, cold ironing has also been included in this chapter, even though a feasibility study was developed without carrying out any tests.

3.1. Fiber Optic Sensor System (ENEA)

Technology Objectives

The characteristics and potential of Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors have been extensively described in WP2 of the CRISTAL project. This type of sensor can be used as a sensing element of a bending plate scale to measure the weight variation of debris accumulated on a weighing pad and to calculate the height of the remaining debris column. In the Po River the FOS is meant to measure the weight and assess the occupation volume of the sand/debris dunes in critical sections to understand to what extent the navigability in that sections can be allowed.

Below are the main elements of the tests run on FBG sensors. For further details, please refer to the deliverables of WP2 (D2.1 and D2.2).

Experimental Setup

Testing of FOS technology were not performed in an operational environment but in laboratory conditions which simulated the accumulation of debris dunes in critical shallow section of Po River. First it is planned to study the feasibility of a weighting pad solution then three sets of tests were run: in dry condition, using a dry test bench to test and calibrate the scale, a tank tests and pool tests.

Dry tests

In the case of the dry test bench, a rectangular plate was made in simple support on the two opposite sides (Figure 3). The support was secured by two rails with a triangular section fixed on a rectangular basement. The material used for the plate and the basement is aluminium. Three FBG sensors were installed on the plate in different positions. The scale was tested in dry conditions using reference masses of 1600 gr each. The blocks were loaded and unloaded slowly one by one to allow the balance to settle. When the weight changes, the sensors show different responses depending on where they are placed.

Figure 3 Scheme of the first weighing pad

Source: ENEA

The measurement acquisition period was about 15 minutes, this did not affect the temperature, which was considered constant for the duration of the experiment. However, FBG sensors are sensitive to temperature and a compensation technique may be needed (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Load and unload tasks in dry operational conditions.

Source: ENEA

The tests carried out show the validity of the prototype

Tank tests

To run the tank tests, the prototype was placed on the bottom of a tank that was filled with water. The FBG sensors were coated with a waterproofing material. Subsequently, coarse sand was poured (Figure 5). In this case, measures were taken to compensate for the variation in water temperature.

Figure 5 Picture of the tank used for the test and the FGB wave-length raw data and processed data by the algorithm to reduce the temperature

Source: ENEA

Pool test

For the pool test a weighing pad has been built as a first semi-engineered prototype (Figure 6). The pad is a large metallic waterproof sealed box instrumented with fiber optic sensors. Both the side and the bottom surfaces of the pad are massive and have structural functions only, whereas the upper surface (referred to as the weighing surface) has controlled elastic properties and performs the weighting function. FBG sensors stay inside the pad and are thus protected from water by the watertight seal of the scale.

Figure 6 Pad features and pool test accessories

Source: ENEA

Preliminary tests were affected by water temperature. It was necessary to compensate for this effect to reduce the impact on the measurements.

The reported data of the weighing pad, once carefully calibrated, can be used as a reliable measure of weight in underwater conditions. The next step is to model the weight of a column of debris and correlate it with its height. In this way it will be possible to enable real-time detection of debris accumulation on the riverbed and allowing for the identification of potential obstacles to navigation.

Conclusions and differentiation compared to the state of the art

Currently, the monitoring of debris along the riverbed is done using special boats equipped with bathymetric devices capable of measuring the depth of the water. The use of a weighing instrument that ensures permanent monitoring of the accumulation of debris through Fiber optic FBG sensors offers the possibility of making a more efficient programming of the dredging activity of the riverbeds with considerable cost savings and an increase in the safety and reliability of navigation. Data generation allows the evaluation and development of digital twins and forecasting models of navigability.

3.2. Acoustic Emissions (CERTh)

Technology Objectives

In May 2023 AE sensors were installed on the the Baricetta lock gates along the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco canal managed by IV, and then on the gates of the Isola Serafini lock along the Pad River managed by AIPO, and collected data on the technical condition of the lock doors (Figure 7).

This paragraph presents the analysis of acoustic emission (AE) monitoring data collected from the waterlock gate at Conca Di Baricetta.

Figure 7 The Conca Di Baricetta waterlock and place of the metallic gate on which experimentations were conducted.

Source: Google Maps

The measurements and experimentation aimed to evaluate / demonstrate the effectiveness of AE-based methodology in distinguishing between normal operational conditions and various simulated failure scenarios at the metallic gates. The monitoring system employed MISTRAS micro-SHM equipment¹ with four sensors (one R6a and three R15a sensors) strategically positioned on the metallic gate structure (Figure 8, Figure 9).

¹ <https://www.physicalacoustics.com/by-product/micro-shm-structural-health-monitoring-system/>

Figure 8 Placement of the AE system sensors, one R6a and three R15a (right to left)
Source: CERTH, own elaboration

Figure 9 Safe placement of AE logger micro-SHM by MISTRAS onto the water lock gate.
Source: CERTH, own elaboration

Experimental Setup

This last experimental campaign consisted of three distinct phases:

1. Normal Operation Baseline

Ten complete open-close cycles of the water lock gate were recorded at two different threshold levels:

- 10 dB threshold with 1 kHz high-pass filter
- 25 dB threshold with identical filtering

Each recording captured the complete acoustic signature of one operational cycle, establishing the Normal Operating Space (NOS) reference.

Figure 10 The sensors cables and used impact hammer.
Source: CERTH, own elaboration

2. Impact Hammer Testing

Simulated mechanical impacts were introduced using an impact hammer with various tips (rubber, aluminium, steel, and plastic) near the sensor locations. This method simulated sudden mechanical failures or impacts that might occur during service (Figure 10, Figure 11).

Figure 11 The impact hammer during corresponding experimentations at the metallic gate and the used hammer tips from rubber, aluminium and plastic (left to right).

Source: CERTH, own elaboration

3. Ultrasonic Excitation

High-frequency failure modes were simulated using an ultrasonic generator producing sinusoidal, pulse, and double exponential signals at: 30 kHz, 40 kHz and 60 kHz.

Data Analysis Methodology

The analysis employed a deviation vector approach, where each recording was compared against a reference NOS recording. Each deviation vector contains 27 components representing various time-domain and frequency-domain features extracted from the AE signals. For visualization and interpretation, three key components were selected:

- Component 3: Time-related metric
- Component 21: Amplitude/energy metric
- Components 23-27: Statistical features

Results and Discussion

This section contains the results as produced by the developed python library detecting upcoming failures based on the deviation of the system from what was considered as a good normal operating space.

1. Normal Operation Characteristics

Figure 12 Mean deviation vector components for normal gate operations

The normal operation vectors (V2-V6) showed relatively consistent patterns with moderate variations in the selected components (Figure 12). The mean values for key components were fluctuation of major

constituents all coming from normal operating water lock gate operations. It can be seen that the fluctuation is extremely small (table 3).

Table 2 Fluctuation of major constituents coming from normal operating water lock gate operations

Component	Mean Value	Standard Deviation
3rd (Time)	0.2169	0.0354
21st (Amplitude)	0.2620	0.1156
23rd	0.1119	0.1570
24th	0.2851	0.2025
25th	0.3718	0.2117
26th	0.2565	0.2643
27th	0.0600	0.0151

Source: CERTH, own elaboration

2. Impulse Hammer Test Results

Figure 13 Comparison of deviation vectors from impulse hammer tests

Source: CERTH, own elaboration

The impact hammer tests produced significantly different acoustic signatures compared to normal operations (Figure 13). Key observations include:

- Component 21 (amplitude) showed dramatic increases, ranging from 15.89 to 264.50, compared to the normal operation mean of 0.262
- Component 23 exhibited substantial variations, with values between 24.99 and 50.00, indicating altered energy distribution
- The time component (3rd) remained relatively stable, suggesting that the impact duration was consistent across tests

3. Ultrasonic Excitation Results

Figure 14 Deviation vectors from ultrasonic excitation at different frequencies

Source: CERTH, own elaboration

The ultrasonic excitation tests revealed distinct patterns (Figure 14):

- Component 21 values ranged from 121.49 to 340.97, intermediate between normal operation and impulse hammer tests
- Component 23 showed extreme values (287.50 to 374.99), indicating strong high-frequency content
- Frequency-dependent responses were observed, with 40 kHz excitation producing the highest component 23 value

4. Comprehensive Comparison

Figure 15 Comparative analysis of all test conditions
 Source: CERTH, own elaboration

The methodology demonstrates excellent discrimination capability between normal operation and failure conditions (Figure 15, Table 14).

Table 3 Table of comparative analysis over all test conditions

Test Condition	Component 21 Range	Component 23 Range	Distinguishability
Normal Operation	0.037 - 0.338	0.0 - 0.392	Baseline
Impulse Hammer	15.89 - 264.50	25.00 - 50.00	Excellent
Ultrasonic	121.49 - 340.97	287.50 - 375.00	Excellent

Source: CERTH, own elaboration

Separation Analysis

The separation factors between failure simulations and normal operation demonstrate the methodology's effectiveness:

Table 4 Separation strategy over different failure testing cases.

Impact Hammer vs Normal Operation	
Component 21 (Amplitude)	102× increase
Component 23	224× increase
Components 24-27	Various increases ranging from 0.5× to 4.5×
Ultrasonic Excitation vs Normal Operation	
Component 21 (Amplitude)	516× increase
Component 23	2,871× increase
Components 24-27	Significant variations indicating frequency-specific responses

Source: CERTH, own elaboration

Conclusions and differentiation compared to the state of the art

The acoustic emission monitoring methodology demonstrated excellent capability in distinguishing between normal operational conditions and various simulated failure modes in the water lock gate structure. The analysis revealed:

1. **Clear Separation:** the deviation vectors showed orders of magnitude differences between normal operation and failure simulations, particularly in components 21 (amplitude) and 23 (energy distribution).
2. **Failure Type Discrimination:** the methodology not only detected anomalies but also distinguished between different failure types - mechanical impacts showed different signatures than high-frequency ultrasonic excitations.
3. **Robust Detection:** the large separation between normal and abnormal conditions suggests high reliability in real-world applications, with minimal risk of false positives or missed detections.
4. **Frequency Sensitivity:** the system successfully captured and differentiated high-frequency phenomena (30-60 kHz), demonstrating capability for detecting incipient failures like crack growth or friction-induced damage.

The methodology's excellence in failure detection is evidenced by the consistent and significant deviations observed across all simulated failure conditions. This validates the approach as a reliable tool for structural health monitoring of critical infrastructure such as water lock gates, where early failure detection is essential for safety and operational continuity.

It can capture even small deviation that are considered pre major failure occurrences thereby enabling early detection allowing the placement of early alerts for maintenance. The evaluation had 100% success, and additional data was gathered for the DT to display. Thereby the evidence on capability and reliability are overwhelming.

3.3. Digital Twin (Fraunhofer, ENEA)

Technology Objectives

In the framework of the CRISTAL project, a Digital Twin (DT) has been developed and tested for the Italian Po River Pilot. The main objective of this tool is to support more reliable and efficient inland waterway transport (IWT) through data-based predictions of river conditions, especially water levels that affect navigability.

The Po River is one of the most important inland waterways in Italy, but it is regularly affected by seasonal fluctuations and sedimentation, which create uncertainty for vessel operators. The DT developed in this pilot aims to reduce this uncertainty by providing short-term forecasts and supporting better planning of vessel movements and port operations.

The Digital Twin is a data-driven forecasting system designed to assess the navigability of key river segments up to 14 days in advance. It combines historical discharge and depth data with meteorological inputs such as rainfall and upstream inflow. A set of machine learning models, including LSTM, GRU, and LSTMNet, was developed and tested to capture both short-term and seasonal changes in river flow.

The forecasts are presented in a web-based dashboard, which translates raw model outputs into actionable information. The system classifies navigability based on vessel draft classes (e.g., 140 cm to 250 cm), highlighting which sections are passable and which are at risk due to low water levels. The dashboard uses colour-coded maps and time series plots to support planning decisions.

The DT water way has the potential to be in connection with two other pilots in CRISTAL: the lock DT (focused on infrastructure monitoring) and the buoy DT (focused on environmental data collection). Together, these can form a more complete picture of the river system, helping both operators and infrastructure managers make coordinated decisions.

The expected benefits of the system are practical and measurable. These include improved planning reliability for barge operators, early detection of low-water bottlenecks, better coordination between river navigation and port operations, and, over time, reduced costs related to delays and maintenance. The system also contributes to a more climate-resilient transport strategy, which is important for future scenarios of more extreme weather conditions.

Testing and verification

Testing of the Digital Twin was carried out in several steps. The first stage focused on validating the model's performance using historical data, mainly from hydrological stations that monitor discharge and water depth along the Po. Several years of data were used to train and test different forecasting models, with special attention paid to sections of the river known to be problematic due to sediment buildup or seasonal low flows.

Various models were compared, including both traditional statistical ones (like ARIMA and VAR) and more modern machine learning models such as LSTM, GRU, and LSTMNet. Among these, the LSTMNet model showed the most balanced performance in terms of prediction accuracy and robustness across different locations.

To test how the system would perform in more operational settings, recent data were used to generate forecasts and compare them to known conditions. This helped identify how sensitive the system is to different patterns and how well it could adapt to new data. The testing showed that the model performs reliably even under less predictable situations.

In parallel, a user interface was developed to present the forecasts in a way that is easy to interpret. This dashboard was shared with relevant stakeholders, including port authorities, infrastructure planners, and logistics coordinators, who provided feedback on how to improve the display, the alerts, and the overall user experience. Their suggestions were implemented, for example by refining the risk classifications and improving trend visualizations.

Finally, efforts were made to ensure that the system could connect with other components in the CRISTAL project. The goal was to check if the DT could exchange data and function in a larger ecosystem of tools for inland waterway management.

The forecasting system was tested mainly on its ability to predict water levels and to correctly classify whether different vessel classes could safely navigate specific river segments in the coming days.

The best performance was achieved using the LSTNet model. This model combines both deep learning and time-series components and was particularly effective in identifying trends over time. It managed to capture both rapid changes, such as those following rainfall and slower seasonal changes.

In terms of numerical results, the average difference between predicted and actual water level values ranged between 8 and 11 centimetres depending on the location. This is within an acceptable range for planning purposes. When the model was used to classify navigability based on vessel draft, it achieved an accuracy rate of over 95%. In other words, in most cases, the system correctly predicted whether a certain ship could pass or not.

Equally important was the model's ability to avoid false positives, cases where navigation is incorrectly predicted to be possible. These cases were kept under 5%, which is considered a strong result, as such errors can be costly or even dangerous.

The figure 16 provides the number of cases for true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), false negatives (FN), and true positives (TP)

Figure 16 Number of cases for true negative, false positive, false negative and true positive
Source: Fraunhofer, own elaboration

The forecasts covered a horizon of up to 14 days, offering a useful window for planning and coordination. Operators can use this information to decide on cargo loads, routes, or timing adjustments in advance.

The dashboard interface was also evaluated and proved helpful for users with varying technical backgrounds. It uses intuitive colour schemes, trend graphs, and tables that highlight where and when problems may occur. This allows users to make informed decisions quickly and with confidence (Figure 17).

Figure 17 Po River Digital Twin dashboard displaying real-time water level data, navigability conditions, and short-term forecasts for critical river sections
Source: Fraunhofer, own elaboration

Deviations from Initial Hypotheses

At the start of the project, the plan included the use of high-frequency, continuous sedimentation data to support the predictive models. In practice, however, such data were limited in availability and coverage across the relevant sections of the Po River. As a result, sedimentation dynamics had to be estimated indirectly, using statistical methods based on historical discharge and depth variation patterns.

Although this was a limitation, the system still performed well thanks to the strength of the machine learning models and the use of recent hydrological and meteorological data.

Conclusions and differentiation compared to the state of the art

The Digital Twin developed for the Po River Pilot has shown clear potential to support the main goals of the CRISTAL project. It contributes directly to several key performance indicators:

Navigability reliability was improved, as the system reduced uncertainty in daily planning and allowed users to anticipate disruptions in advance.

Synchromodal corridor management system was supported by more accurate visibility of short-term water depth forecasts, helping coordinate vessel arrivals.

Beyond the formal KPIs, several broader observations can be made. First, the DT acts as a connector, it brings together different sources of data and translates them into something useful for transport decisions. Second, users engaged positively with the dashboard during the pilot phase. Their feedback was constructive and indicated that the tool could be adopted more widely. Third, the architecture of the system is flexible enough to be used in other regions or adapted for different transport corridors.

The current version of the Digital Twin offers a solid base, but further improvements are possible. These include:

- Adding higher-frequency sedimentation sensors to improve the accuracy of bottom depth forecasts.
- Using satellite imagery or remote sensing data to cover areas where ground-based monitoring is limited.
- Connecting the DT with older management systems in ports and infrastructure to improve compatibility.
- Expanding the forecasting models to simulate long-term changes in climate and their impact on navigability.

3.4. Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (CERTH)

Technology Objectives

The Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS) is an online platform (Figure 18) designed to collect, consolidate, and distribute current and forecasted river disruption-related information to operational stakeholders. This information is also used to support operational decisions for the planning and re-planning of operations, combined with the visibility into alternative routes that the SCMS provides. Additionally, the collected data is analysed to provide valuable input for decision-making and policymaking at the regional level (Figure 19).

Figure 18: Home page of the Synchro-modal Corridor Management System, showing the Po river
Source: CERTH

Figure 19 Main features of the SCMS (as displayed in the Home page)

Source: CERTH, own elaboration

System implementation and components

The SCMS is a centralized digital system (platform) that is installed on the servers of CERTH, at its main facilities. The setup of the system for the case of the Italian pilot initially involved the input of all geospatial information of the river Po and the Canal and the related infrastructure (river ports, bridges, locks), as well as the segmentation of the fairway with their characteristics (speed limits, compatible barge classes based on the classification of European Inland Waterways²). This work served as the foundation for the development of the core functions and services of the SCMS in the area.

The SCMS as implemented in the Po river consists of all four main functionalities that were developed in the context of CRISTAL, namely the:

1. Early detection and info service

This functionality consolidates forecasted disruption impacts on Inland Waterway (IWW) operations in river Po and the Canal, by receiving structured data from the CRISTAL Digital Twin developed by Fraunhofer through an API in a predefined JSON form. This includes two types of alerts: the first is related to expected operational disruptions due to possible failures in the metallic doors of locks along the Po River and the Canal, as these emerge from the analysis of data that come from the implementation of the Acoustics Emission (AE) system. The second is related to expected changes in the navigable depth of the river Po outside the predefined limits based on the river vessels compatibility class, due to draught or floods, as these emerge from the analysis of historical and daily data from sensors implemented along the entire navigable part of the river Po.

This dataset is further enriched by integrating alerts and notifications from existing external sources and legacy systems, such as the Notices to Skippers (NtS), published daily from the infrastructure managers of Po

² <https://unece.org/DAM/trans/doc/finaldocs/sc3/TRANS-SC3-131e.pdf>

and the Canal (AIPo & Infrastrutture Venete) and include any other type of disruption that may affect the river operations.

All this consolidated information is made available to the system user upon request through the system's dashboard (Figure 20), also providing them with a customization option (information source, time period).

A configurable push notification service is also implemented to disseminate relevant updates to registered stakeholders, leveraging user-defined preference profiles to ensure targeted and context-specific information delivery. More specifically, the user can select the river of interest and the source of information (in this case, AIPo, Infrastrutture Venete and the Digital twins) to receive daily updates on the available alerting information.

Figure 20: Disruption information in river Po as presented in the SCMS platform for a user-defined time period

Source: CERTH, own elaboration

2. Disruption impacts identification service

This functionality enables a comprehensive assessment of the impact of disruptions on logistics operations by leveraging both existing alerts and forecasted disruption data from the Digital Twin. It supports user-initiated requests to evaluate the feasibility of planned transport routes, considering current and anticipated network conditions (Figure 21).

1 Select River

Po Seine Moselle Vistula

2 Origin - Destination

Select Origin-Destination Ports:

Manually
 Automatically

Choose Point on Map and Calculate the Departure Port

Porto di Cremona

Destination Port

Porto di Valdaro

3 Vessel

River Class Compatibility

Class III

Not every type of vessel can navigate all parts of the river.

Cargo Type

Dry Bulk

Cargo in Tons

175

Vessel Network

Show the Shortest Route

Figure 21 Selection of Origin and Destination, vessel type and cargo characteristics for the route assessment
Source: CERTH, own elaboration

Additionally, the platform provides detailed insights, including CO₂ emission estimation, expected time of arrival (ETA), and specific information about the nature and origin of disruptions (if any) along planned routes, thus enhancing operational planning, risk mitigation, and sustainability monitoring. It also provides visibility to the alternative modes routes that can be used to complement or substitute the assessed river routes, supporting dynamic mode shifts in response to disruptions or changing conditions according to the Synchronodality principles. These results are made available to the system user through the system's dashboard (Figure 22, Figure 23, Figure 24).

Figure 22 Example of a (feasible) route assessment result
Source: CERTH, own elaboration

Figure 23 Example of a (non-feasible) route assessment result, providing also the relevant disruption information
Source: CERTH, own elaboration

Figure 24 Example of rail and road alternatives to the planned river route.
Source: CERTH, own elaboration

3. Action toolbox of services

This functionality includes a modular toolbox of value-added services, customized to the specific requirements of each inland waterway corridor. In the case of the Italian pilot, these services include:

- a dashboard with forecasted river navigability maps, which is the graphic representation of the Smart Bulletin developed in the context of the pilot activities (Figure 25). Using this tool, the user can select the time period of his interest along with the vessel class he intends to use, and the system displays the forecasted navigability status (green – navigable, red – non navigable) in all segments of the river Po and the Canal for the specific vessel class. This time period can be extended up to 2 weeks from the current date.

Figure 25 The Smart Bulletin dashboard for river Po and the Canal.

Source: CERTH, own elaboration

- a dashboard for calculating the ETA of the optimal river route for a specific origin and destination, using as input (from the system user) the average vessel speed and the average delay on the locks along the route (Figure 26).

Figure 26 Example of ETA calculation in the river Po and the Canal, considering average speed and lock delays

Source: CERTH, own elaboration

All tools of the “Action toolbox of services” aim to enhance situational awareness and thus operational efficiency of the inland navigation system of river Po and the Canal. The system architecture allows for the addition of more services in the future if requested, such as real-time track & trace and CO₂ emission calculators.

4. Corridor observatory

The last functionality of the platform features a Corridor Observatory, which includes a River Infrastructure Index and a River Infrastructure metrics tab (Figure 27), designed to monitor the status and performance of key inland waterway assets. In addition, it incorporates an operational metrics tab for monitoring the efficiency of inland transport operations (Figure 28).

The Corridor Observatory in its final form will include static information about the river Po and the Canal and for the relevant infrastructure (river ports, locks and bridges), along with metrics related to the performance of infrastructure (i.e. locks availability, river navigability) and operational efficiency (e.g. CO₂ emissions savings estimations).

Figure 27 Example of river Po and the Canal infrastructure index representation in the corridor observatory
Source: CERTH, own elaboration

Figure 28 Example of CO₂ emission savings KPI representation in the river Po and the Canal corridor observatory

Source: CERTH, own elaboration

By collecting, recording, and analysing both operational and infrastructure-related metrics, the system provides enhanced visibility into corridor conditions. This data-driven approach supports informed decision-making for transport operators and authorities, while also serving as a strategic tool for regional policymakers to evaluate infrastructure performance, identify investment needs, and develop long-term policy frameworks.

Testing and verification

In the context of the system testing process, the following activities took place:

AIPo Notices to Skippers/Smart Bulletin Data Transmission

AIPo has developed a system that sends digitalized Notices to Skippers in JSON format to a dedicated SCMS REST API, so that they can be presented to the SCMS users in the pages for Early Detection and Disruption Impact Estimation functionalities.

AIPo has also developed water level prediction models for the Po River. With the help of a computer system, these predictions are sent in JSON format to a dedicated REST API of the SCMS, so that they can be presented to the Smart Bulletin SCMS page.

In the context of the above data communications, the following testing activities have taken place:

- **APIs request body testing:** Multiple testing sessions were carried out to ensure the overall effectiveness of the data transferring process. The JSON format that was decided to be used to model the Notices to Skippers and the Smart Bulletin data to be transferred to the SCMS, was:
 - Verified from both CERTH and AIPo during dedicated bilateral synchronization meetings
 - Tested for its validity by sending a JSON request body of said format by AIPo to SCMS via HTTP request to the appropriate REST API
- **Communication verification and transmitted data testing:** The AIPo system and SCMS communication was verified for the transmission of the appropriate data. Multiple user acceptance tests were performed in the Early Detection & Info, Disruption Impact Estimation and Smart Bulletin pages to ensure that the Notices to Skippers and Smart Bulletin data are shown correctly.

Loading of Po's historical and infrastructure data into SCMS Observatory

AIPo has provided CERTH with a set of historical water levels data for the Po River, as well as with infrastructure data for it like locks and bridges. These data give the SCMS users the opportunity to see a complete image not only for the navigability of the Po River in the course of time, but also regarding specific metrics and KPIs regarding the river's infrastructure. For this data to exist in and be presented inside the SCMS, the following testing procedures and activities have been followed:

- **Water levels historical and infrastructure data loading:** A PHP script was created where the relevant data are loaded in the SCMS database via a transaction. Appropriate error handling was implemented so that if there were any data defects or computer/software system errors, a rollback happens for the transaction so that the data loading is cancelled. If the data and the successful importing of them inside the database is validated, the script ends with a successful status code and message for the user/programmer.
- **Smart Bulletin and Corridor Observatory pages testing:** After the successful loading of the above data, rigorous user acceptance testing was performed in the Smart Bulletin and Corridor Observatory pages, to ensure that the loaded data are displayed and loaded correctly according to users' input.

SCMS functionalities testing

As part of the system's testing, in addition to the technical tests described above, extensive tests were also carried out to evaluate the usability of the system's functions. More specifically, realistic data sets of alerts were created and uploaded to the system's database, and the response of all system functions was examined under various possible usage scenarios (e.g. feasible and non-feasible routes, alternative route options with the other transport modes).

Overall, the system response to the testing activities was positive both regarding the technical tests that took place for the system connectivity with data sources and the operation of the System's data base and also the functionalities of the system where the system responded as expected giving correct and realistic results.

However, it should be noted that these activities were realised with simulated data created for testing purposes. The connection of the SCMS to the actual data sources and the establishment of real data flow is ongoing to be finalised near the end of the project, at which point further testing will be conducted.

Finally, with respect to deviations in the case of the Italian pilot, the alternative route calculations take into account the existing rail network to explore potential rail-based options. While these alternatives help illustrate multimodal possibilities, it is important to note that regular or dedicated rail services directly linked to the river ports are not yet established. Therefore, the current consideration of rail alternatives remains conceptual and would benefit from future developments in service availability and infrastructure alignment.

Conclusions and differentiation compared to the state of the art:

1. Benefits for navigation in Po and advances beyond the State of the Art (SotA)

The SCMS is a system that provides visibility of the infrastructure and navigability status of river Po and the Canal, supporting also the decision making of operators both in case of normal circumstances and in calamity situations. This enhanced awareness of the river conditions, as well as of the alternative transport options beyond the river, results in better connectivity with the two land-based modes (road and rail). It also contributes to increased resilience of the overall transport system along the corridor and, more specifically, to improved reliability of inland waterway transport, leading to increased attractiveness of inland navigation to cargo flows.

In addition, having insight into the specific causes of disruptions allows for more efficient resource management within the system (e.g., reduced loading in cases of drought or low water levels), thereby ensuring greater capacity during crisis periods.

With respect to SCMS advancements beyond the state of the art, similarly to the implementation of the SCMS in the other two pilot sites in Poland and France, the main innovations of the SCMS can be summarized to the following:

- it estimates the navigability status of the river for assessing planned routes not only considering the current situation (existing published alerts) but also considering forecasted issues through its connection to the Digital Twins of the project (i.e. forecasting water depths and infrastructure (lock) failure). In the case of water levels, the forecasts can be extended up to two weeks ahead.
- it is a single place (one-stop-shop) for getting all alerting information (current and forecasted alerts coming from all available sources) related to the river status (infrastructure and navigability)
- it provides visibility to the other two land mode alternatives (road/rail), supporting the collaboration between the three modes and the integration of inland navigation to a multimodal transportation system along the corridor.

3.5. Navigability Conditions Prediction Model (AIPO, ENEA) and Smart Bulletin (AIPO)

Technology objectives

The picture below (Figure 29) shows the high-level diagram of the subdivision into hardware components related to the part of the CRISTAL under development by AIPO. In addition to the internal components (AIPO IT system), evidence is given of the external components to which the AIPO system will have to interact the related interface.

Figure 29 Hardware components

The AIPO IT system will be composed by two distinct environments: a first environment dedicated to development; a second environment, with better hardware characteristics, dedicated to production.

The following table (Table 6) summarizes the characteristics of the hardware resources expected for both environments:

Table 5 Characteristics of the hardware resources

	Core (#)	RAM (GB)	HD Base (GB)	HD SSD (GB)	I 'm. ARC (GB)
Virtual Machine AS Prod.	16	32	-	100	-
Virtual Machine AS Dev.	8	16	100	-	-
DB Oracle Prod.	10	32	-	800	100
DB Oracle Dev.	8	22	700	-	100
I 'm. ARC for DB backup	-	-	-	-	1300
Total	42	102	800	900	1500

The Operating System provided for Virtual Machines (both for Application Servers and for databases) is Oracle Linux 8. The Oracle database version used is 19c.

The navigable part of the Po River includes a series of shallow waters point that in some hydrometric conditions, do not allow or introduce risks to navigation. The navigable part has been divided into branch within which there are various shallow waters (low depth points) potentially source of interruption of the navigability of the entire section.

To allow an adequate planning of navigation activities on the river, considering the logistical and travel problems, the availability of tools capable of providing useful information on the river navigability condition in each section, even in forecast, is essential for a correct planning and could be an attractive prospect for future developments of this sector.

The statistical model was developed considering the following data:

- GIS information for each low-point and reaches subdivision for the entire Po river;
- dataset of measured water depth collected daily since 1988 for several know critical points (low points);
- historical data of water levels ad derived discharges at each water level gauge;
- +10 days forecasted discharges provided by hydrological models from the Flood and Drought Early Warning System (forecast application);

Statistical model development: phases

If we analyse the evolution of water depth data at one single critical point (i.e. “Fronte Boretto”) and observed discharges at the nearest water level station (i.e. “Boretto”) we can see that there is a good correlation between discharges and water depth. If we try to evaluate the variability of water depth at each discharge value, we can assume that the variation is strictly related to a morphological variation in terms of bathymetry due to a flood events (i.e. solid transport, dune and ripple migration, etc.) or artificial events (i.e. dredging, hydraulic structures). (Figure 30, Figure 31)

Figure 30 Analysis of water depth

Figure 31 Correlation between discharges at Boretto and water depth at critical point “Fronte Boretto”

The probability of navigability at each low point could be evaluated using historical data as follow:

$$P_{cr.point}(nav)|Q_{obs} = \frac{N \text{ of days where depth } \geq \text{minimum class depth and } Q \leq Q_{obs}}{\text{Total N of days where } Q \leq Q_{obs}}$$

Figure 33 Temporal variation of water depth and discharge relation
 Source: AIPo

Smart bulletin

To achieve all the objectives, set out in the GA, related to the Smart Bulletin Generator, a system architecture was defined, which is schematised in the flow chart below (Figure 34):

Figure 34 Smart Bulletin Generator
 Source: AIPo, own elaboration

The entire process to generate the Smart Bulletin is divided in the following phases:

1. Acquisition by external sensors of daily values relating to fairway depth, hydrometric values and flow rate, which will be automatically or manually entered the dB currently in use by the Inland Navigation Department developed in Access. This process, in the first instance, will lead to the generation of an NtS which, via an API, will send the information regarding any disruptions to the SCMS.
2. At the same time, an Oracle dB will be generated that will extract from the Access dB all the information necessary to populate and run both the statistical model and the ML model; the statistical model developed by AIPo will be allocated on an AIPo server, while the allocation of the ML developed by ENEA/Fraunhofer is still to be defined (it may reside on the same server of the statistical model or in an external environment and send the results to the AIPo server through an API;
3. The results produced by the two models are acquired by a 'Decision Making Model', that is being designing, to select the navigability condition forecast results that will generate the Smart Bulletin that will also be sent to the SCMS via API. Below is the Smart Bulletin in its final version. (Figure A).

The smart bulletin consists of a table with four sections of the River Po Form Cremona to Mantua. The locations represent nodes in the waterway system where interchange of goods with road or rail carriers is possible (Figure 35).

For each section, the navigability conditions at all critical points are reported. The lowest navigability value is selected among all the critical points on a given segment. Green indicates that all critical points in a section are navigable. The analysis is performed for each day and considering the different vessel draft classes.

Figure 35 Smart Bulletin

Test results

For a correct evaluation of both statistical and ML models, the first step is a definition of adequate metrics capable of showing the performance for the final model goals. In the Po River case, the model should be used to provide a Boolean answer for each reach of the river, hence a binary prediction of navigable or not navigable.

For that kind of binary forecast models, a good evaluation of their performance is commonly derived by contingency table and the related indexes. A contingency table is composed of a 2x2 matrix where the axes are the model and the observed event respectively compared to a defined threshold (binary division).

Table 6 Contingency table

PO RIVER NAVIGABILITY FORECAST STATISTIC MODEL		OBSERVED		
		No	Yes	TOTAL
MODEL	No	HIT	FA	HIT+FA
	Yes	MA	CN	MA+CN
	TOTAL	HIT+MA	FA+CN	HIT+FA+CA+CN

Where:

HIT – Correct forecast

FA – False Alarm

MA – Missed Alarm

CN – Correct negative

The indexes derived are:

Table 7 Performance Indexes

Indexes		Formula
CSI	<i>Critical Success Index</i>	$HIT/(HIT+MA+FA)$
POD	<i>Prob. Of Detection</i>	$HIT/(HIT+MA)$
FAR	<i>False Alarm Ratio</i>	$FA/(HIT+FA)$
F	<i>False detection rate</i>	$FA/(FA+CN)$
ACC	<i>Accuracy</i>	$(HIT+CN)/(HIT+CN+FA+MA)$
SR	<i>Success Ratio</i>	$HIT/(HIT+FA)$
MAR	<i>Missed Alarm Ratio</i>	$MA/(HIT+MA)$

Statistical model

For each critical point and also for the entire dataset the complete indexes are calculated. To obtain an unbiased validation the entire dataset was divided in two different sub-sets, the calibration dataset containing all data from 2000 to 2022 and the validation dataset composed by the remaining data from 2023 to 2024.

In order to obtain a binary response (nav / non nav.) we fixed a probability threshold (i.e. 70%), and the overall results are the following (navigation class 140 cm, all sites):

PO RIVER NAVIGABILITY FORECAST STATISTICAL MODEL		OBSERVED		
		No	Yes	Total
MODEL	No	4792	10631	15423
	Yes	746	87086	87832
	Total	5538	97717	103255

Indexes actual		
CSI	0,296	<i>Critical Success Index</i>
POD	0,865	<i>Prob. Of Detection</i>
FAR	0,689	<i>False Alarm Ratio</i>
F	0,109	<i>False detection rate</i>
ACC	0,890	<i>Accuracy</i>
SR	0,311	<i>Success Ratio</i>
MAR	0,135	<i>Missed alarm ratio</i>

The overall results showed a good performance in terms of accuracy and probability of detection, although a more accurate indexes can be achieved defining not an overall but a site-specific analysis and probability threshold. In the following table, a site-specific analysis with optimized threshold is showed (Table 8).

Table 8 Site specific analysis and probability threshold

REACH	SITE	POD	FAR	ACC	SR
CASALMAGGIORE	CASALMAGGIORE	1,000	0,000	0,767	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	F. PENN. GUSSOLA	1,000	0,000	0,877	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	FOSSACAPRARA	0,925	0,081	0,851	0,925
CASALMAGGIORE	FRONTE CASALMAGGIORE	1,000	0,000	0,811	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	FRONTE CASELLA ROSSA	0,895	0,118	0,863	0,895
CASALMAGGIORE	FRONTE CICOGNARA	1,000	0,000	0,910	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	FRONTE CURVA N. 31	1,000	0,000	0,832	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	V. CHIAVICA TORRICELLA	0,991	0,010	0,940	0,991
CASALMAGGIORE	VALLE CASALMAGGIORE	1,000	0,000	0,860	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	VALLE FOCE PARMA	1,000	0,000	0,867	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	VALLE PENNELLO COGOZZO	1,000	0,000	0,833	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	VALLE PENNELLO SACCA	1,000	0,000	0,877	1,000

Machine Learning model (LSTM model)

Respect the statistical approach, where the results are the navigation probability, with a ML model the results are the best estimation of a forecasted water depth, hence a direct Boolean answer can be obtained using the navigation class maximum depth as a threshold.

Due to its complexity in terms of computation, the model for the entire river is still in progress. The first validation scores are available only for some reaches. The following indexes are calculated on the simulated results from 2019 to 2023:

Indexes actual		
CSI	0,615	<i>Critical Success Index</i>
POD	0,861	<i>Prob. Of Detection</i>
FAR	0,317	<i>False Alarm Ratio</i>
F	0,032	<i>False detection rate</i>
ACC	0,961	<i>Accuracy</i>
SR	0,683	<i>Success Ratio</i>
MAR	0,139	<i>Missed alarm ratio</i>

Conclusions and differentiation compared to the state of the art:

Current Notice to Skippers only reports the measured water depth at critical points. The added value compared to the state of the art is having a separate bulletin with navigability forecasts for multiple days and according to vessel class.

The 10-day period was chosen considering a round trip from Cremona to Venice that typically takes that time (voyage + loading/unloading). The bulletin will be available on the AiPo website, and the data will be communicated to the SCMS via a specially developed API.

3.6. Cold Ironing (Infrastrutture Venete)

Technology Objectives

As described in the previous D7.1, a key contribution to CRISTAL activities by IV is represented by a feasibility study testing the possibility of developing a dedicated network of cold ironing facilities along the two branches represented by Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante and Po-Brondolo canals³ and exploring the possibility of further replicability along others, mainly touristic routes, such as the Idrovia Litoranea Veneta.

In particular, the second part of D.7.1 was specifically dedicated to describing the feasibility studies. Concerning the implementation process, following the accomplishment of the feasibility study a relevant follow-up activity is currently ongoing an activity addressing the design of a "typical plant" model of cold ironing facility (thus paving the way to possible future implementation beyond the scope and timeline of CRISTAL project). More specifically, this activity involves producing detailed design documents referring to different specific locations, each one representing a particular typology of landing point. This process is

³ In the D7.1 and in the following the entire system has been referred to as the "Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco waterway" (implicitly also including the Po di Levante and Po-Brondolo sections). These two interconnected waterways constitute, respectively, the outlets towards the Adriatic Sea and the Venice lagoon for the waterway starting from Mantua.

enabling the further consolidation and finalization of preliminary cost estimates, taking into account the substantial impact of auxiliary works and setup (e.g., wiring and, where applicable, the construction of MV/LV transformer electrical substations), which depend on the unique conditions of each port or mooring area.

The feasibility study has addressed the challenge of providing shoreside electrical power for the energy demands of ships calling at port/berths, allowing them to switch off their auxiliary diesel generators (and consequently reducing related gas and noise emissions). Furthermore, the new infrastructure will be ready to receive innovative units endowed with electric or hybrid propulsion as well as to fully follow the EU Commission's indications on a decarbonized transport future.

IV has carried out a feasibility study on cold ironing. However, this study has not included a pilot or on-site realisation and testing.

Hence, the activity is not related to testing a new technological solution, while the innovative character is related to adopting a systemic approach addressing a whole set of waterways.

In this regard, it is also worth noting that the analysis was developed starting from two relevant prior achievements:

- a) Technical specifications for cold ironing» approved by the Technical-Administrative Consultative Commission of the Interregional Agreement for Po River and linked IWWs
- b) First pilot cold ironing site at the Rovigo Interporto with funding from the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) which have nothing in common/connected with the ones of the CRISTAL project.

Within the analysis, an interdisciplinary approach has been adopted that allows to leverage on synergies related to a vision encompassing:

- Freight and passenger transport with a relevant deal paid to sustainable tourism;
- Intermodality;
- Cold ironing and recharge of electric units.

Among other things, this implied setting up an action plan with reference to different steps and time horizons. To this end a relevant deal has been paid to thoroughly mapping the state of play in each landing point and understanding needs and technological solutions, both through questionnaire as well as interviews with the stakeholders and on-site surveys of the state-of-play of each landing point, as specified more in detail in D7.1.

IV is focusing on the topic of energy supply to boats using the waterway and in particular on the possibility to develop a dedicated supporting infrastructure to provide both renewable energy production at local level and an adequate typology of devices to be used for charging e-boats or for plug-in services for boats.

The key outcome of the activity is a detailed definition of the facilities which are proposed to be developed and installed for this purpose in each landing point according to the following ideal sequence of steps (see D7.1):

- Phase 0 – “Interporto di Rovigo – state of play in 2024”
- Phase 1 – “ready to go” in 2025

- Phase 2 – “fast followers” in 2026-27
- Phase 3 – “Future projects” in 2030

Below is a summary representation of the waterway axes with the location of the landing places addressed by the development phases proposed. The colouring of the dots referring to the phases of the scenarios described above.

Figure 36 Location of the interventions Fissero Tartaro Canalbianco Po di Levante waterway
Source: Own elaboration

Figure 37 Location of the interventions Po – Brondolo waterway

Source: Own elaboration

Still in absence of an actual test, a complete answer to this question cannot be provided. Anyhow, a comment on the outcome of the study can be surely associated with the ascertained:

- Complexity and interdisciplinary character of the addressed theme, also requiring active involvement and cooperation with different stakeholders
- Importance of the environmental benefits that can be achieved (reduction of CO₂ emissions and air & noise pollution at local level)
- importance of maximizing synergy with
 - Energy provisions from renewable sources
 - Electric propulsion
 - Sustainable tourism
- Importance of integrating comprehensive and (regularly) updated data regarding both the infrastructure and facilities on the supply side as well as on the transport demand
- Need for strategic and comprehensive vision to be implemented through a step-by-step approach

Conclusions and differentiation compared to the state of the art:

A future implementation Cold Ironing is expected in particular a reduction of emissions due to possibility of switching off engines while mooring. In the analysed context (in this case, focusing specifically on the Fissero-Tartaro-CanalBianco waterway), this is particularly relevant in the case of cruise ships for touristic purposes, to which are referred the values reported in the table. The reported figures can be considered as a conservative estimation of reduced emission due to efficiency and less polluting sources represented by electric energy supply. Among other things the implementation of further synergic measures is not considered (e.g. adoption of electric propulsion units).

4. Living Labs (SOGESCA)

Objectives of the task

As part of the Italian pilot, two Living Labs were organized with the aim of bringing together inland navigation stakeholders and identifying a shared path for the improvement of the waterway. The first Living lab was held on 13th March 2024 and involved waterway users. The second involved public bodies and took place on 16th April 2024.

The results of the living labs are contained in a document that represents the manifesto for the development of the Padano-Veneto waterway system. This document was signed by infrastructure users, local institutions, and business representatives and shared with the Italian Ministry of Infrastructure.

4.1. Manifesto (SOGESCA)

Objective of the document

The purpose of the *Manifesto for the Sustainable Development of the Padano-Veneto Inland Waterway System* is to contribute practical insight for the sustainable development of the Padano-Veneto waterway system, ensuring increasingly reliable, efficient, economically competitive, user-friendly, and climate resilient waterway transport for goods and people.

Principles and general objectives stick to United Nations 2030 Agenda for sustainable development, and specifically:

- Goal 9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation
- Goal 13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts
- Goal 17. Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development

During the Living Labs, the Stakeholders (users, public authorities, infrastructure managers, trade associations, project partners) shared challenges, needs and potential solutions, as summarised in the table below:

Table 9 Challenges, needs and potential solutions of inland navigation

Issue	Challenges	Proposed solutions	Recipients of interventions
Governance	Communication among the various stakeholders Lack of a shared vision	Regular meetings between port and inland port operators, Intesa, users and other actors	Provinces, Rovigo Interporto, Riverside municipalities, UNII, Intesa, Infrastrutture Venete (IV), AIPo, ARSTPC

Infrastructure	Bridge height allowing the passage of Class V CEMT convoys	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ensure operational continuity for project already approved and funded by IV 2. Secure funding for non-financed interventions 3. Develop an integrated bridge development plan 	Infrastructure Owner (RFI, Municipalities, Anas, etc.), MIT, Intesa
	Maintenance of locks: planning, scheduling and communication	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lock monitoring plan 2. Routine maintenance plan subject to prior consultation with users 3. Extraordinary maintenance: Prompt communication to users and adherence to the scheduled timeline 	AIPo, IV, ARSTPC, Intesa
	Sediment accumulation: critical points along the waterway where sediment reduces the available draft	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enhance dredging activities reviewing the needed budget 2. Revise the approach to dredging activities: outsourcing, partnership with privates, etc. 3. implement a daily depth bulletin with five- and ten-day forecasts (CRISTAL) 4. Performing extraordinary re-sectioning of the navigable channel in artificial canals. 	AIPo, IV, ARSTPC, Intesa
	Management of dredged sediment	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collaboration between infrastructure managers and other entities that can re-use the material 2. Re-use to reinforce embankments 	AIPo, IV, ARSTPC, Regions
	Bank cleaning: maintenances and cleaning of the river	Provide adequate funding in order to	Intesa

	banks to ensure the visibility of navigation signals	outsource the service of cleaning	
	Cleaning of bridge piers of debris buildup	Prompt intervention by bridge manager/operator	Bridge manager
Tourism navigation	Tourist docks: mooring difficulties due to shallow waters; lack of action by dock operator to remove debris	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Dredging near private docks, using regional funding if needed 2. Communication of water depth (Portolano del Po, App) 	Regions, AIPo/AdBPo, IV, ARSTPC
	Lack of clear information on services and prices at certain docks	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define minimum service level at docks 2. Enhance the range of services offered 3. dock managers provide information on services and mooring fees (also publishing them on Portolano del Po) 4. Cold Ironing (CRISTAL) and map of dock along Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbiano on IV website 5. Integrate Portolano del Po with links to IV and RER website 	Docks operator, AIPo/AdBPo, IV, Intesa
Commercial navigation	Commercial ports: difficulties in finding information on mooring fees and services online	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. dedicated sections on website of the Provinces and inland port 2. Create a specific website for the Port of Cremona and Mantua 3. Add port-related information on AIPo and IV websites 	Province of Mantua, Province of Cremona, AIPo, IV
Inland navigation personnel	Lack of a national collective employment contract for inland navigation personnel; Existing legal provisions (art 375 Codice della Navigazione) outdated	Creation of a working group to discuss proposal for a national collective contract for inland navigation personnel.	Trade Unions, Employer organisations, Ministry of Labour and Social Policies

	and inadequate to current context; Use of collective contract		
	Shortage of onboard personnel: professional qualifications inadequate to meet current needs of the sector; lack of interoperability with maritime rules	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Urgent revision of the regulation on professional qualification for inland navigation under DPR n. 631/1949 and DPR n. 332/1957 2. New legislation introducing a simplified equivalency system between maritime and inland navigation professional qualifications 	MIT, Ministry of Educational and Merit, Ministry of Health, Ministry of Labor and Social Policies, Civil Motor Vehicle Authority, Trade Unions and employer association
	Shortage of personnel in the Civil Motor Vehicle Authority dedicated to navigation related procedures	Ensure staffing level are adequate to meet specific regional needs	MIT
Regulatory sector	Legislative Decree n. 114/2018, technical requirement for vessels used in inland navigation: the fees set by 10 th May 2022, are extremely high and have a negative impact on the stakeholders	Urgent revision of the decree 10 th May 2022 by MIT to achieve a reasonable reduction in fees.	MIT
	Incentives for the development and enhancement of a freight transport and tourism via inland and river-sea waterways: the requirements set by Ministerial Decree n. 476/2020 for accessing the idrobonus appear too restrictive; state aid does not cover the tourism sector	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Extend idorbonus to maritime vessels that undertake commercial trips to inland ports 2. Allow the contracting transport company to be a pro-rata beneficiary of the idrobonus 3. Increase the idorbonus coefficient 4. Specific measure for tourism sector regarding state aid for the modernization of inland navigation fleet 	MIT

	Access to seaport for inland navigation vessels	Adjust the fees according to the tonnage of the vessels	Post System Authority
	Coastal navigation by inland vessels: absence of additional technical requirements allowing inland navigation vessels to extend their navigation up to three miles from the coast; inland navigation personnel is not allowed to operate in protected water	1. Address these two issues urgently in order to prevent imbalance in the market 2. RIS directive adoption is a prerequisite to enable inland navigation vessels to operate along the coast	MIT
	RIS- River Information Services activation	Adoption of the Directive 2005/44/EC	MIT

4.2. Gap Analysis (SOGESCA)

Objective of the action

The gap analysis aims to assess if the organisational model of an entity (private company or public body) complies with the climate change mitigation and adaptation international standards and EU policies (identified in task 3.2) and is able to ensure resilience to the impacts of climate change and smooth functioning of its businesses/activities/operations related to the IWW in case of extreme events. Stakeholders were also informed about the initiative through the living labs and were selected based on their request to voluntarily carry out the gap analysis of their organisation.

a) Cross-cutting Summary – GAP Analysis of some private companies connected with the Inland Waterways system

SOGESCA conducted the analyses within the framework of the European project Horizon Europe CRISTAL to assess the organisational positioning of ten companies in the inland waterway transport and intermodal logistics sector, primarily focusing on climate resilience and sustainability.

The evaluations covered four thematic areas:

- a) Management systems
- b) Climate change mitigation and adaptation actions
- c) ESG sustainability
- d) Business continuity

The methodology was based on structured questionnaires, qualitative and quantitative evaluations, with scores expressed as percentages relative to an ideal state of full compliance.

a) Management Systems

The companies exhibit a heterogeneous situation regarding management systems. Overall, there is a good level of adoption of quality (ISO 9001⁴) and health and safety (ISO 45001⁵) certifications, whereas environmental (ISO 14001⁶) and energy (ISO 50001⁷) certifications are still relatively uncommon. Some organisations have integrated multiple standards into a single management system, demonstrating greater organisational maturity, whilst others rely on informal internal procedures.

Knowledge of additional standards, such as ISO 27001⁸ for information security, ISO 37001⁹ for anti-bribery, and UNI/PdR 125¹⁰ for gender equality, is widespread but seldom implemented in practice. The formalisation of organisational models under Legislative Decree 231/2001¹¹ and the adoption of ethical codes are only evident in certain instances.

Identified shortcomings:

- Limited implementation of ISO 14001 and ISO 50001.
- Lack of structured policies on corporate social responsibility.
- Incomplete adoption of Legislative Decree 231/2001 models.

⁴ ISO 9001 is an internationally recognized standard for quality management systems (QMS). It provides a framework for organisations of all sizes and sectors to improve their performance, meet customer expectations and demonstrate their commitment to quality. Its requirements define how to establish, implement, maintain, and continually improve a quality management system.

⁵ ISO 45001 is an international standard for occupational health and safety management systems. It helps organisation to manage and reduce risks associated with workplace safety and health, ultimately aiming to prevent injuries, ill-health, and fatalities.

⁶ ISO 14001 is an international standard for Environmental Management Systems (EMS). It provides a framework for organisations to manage their environmental impact, improve environmental performance, and comply with relevant legal requirements. It covers areas like resource usage, waste management, monitoring environmental performance, and stakeholder involvement.

⁷ ISO 50001 provides a framework for establishing, implementing, maintaining, and improving an energy management system (EnMS). Implementing ISO 50001 can lead to improved energy efficiency, reduced energy costs, enhanced compliance with regulations, and a stronger commitment to sustainability.

⁸ ISO 27001 is an international standard that provides a framework for organisations of all size and sectors to manage and protect their information assets by identifying, assessing, and mitigating information security risks.

⁹ ISO 37001 is an international standard that provides a framework for establishing, implementing, maintaining, and improving an anti-bribery management system (ABMS).

¹⁰ UNI/PdR 125 defines the criteria for certifying gender equality in companies. This certification, issued by accredited bodies, attests to the company's commitment to equality and inclusion, evaluating policies and practices in six key areas: culture and strategy, governance, HR processes, growth opportunities, pay equity, and parental protection.

¹¹ D.L 231/2001 aims to prevent the commission of crimes by legal entities, promote a culture of legality and responsibility within organisations, and ensure greater transparency and fairness in economic and financial activities. A key innovation is the adoption of an Organisation, Management, and Control Model (Model 231), a set of procedures, protocols, and measures aimed at preventing the commission of crimes by employees or collaborators of the entity.

Recommendations:

- Extend existing systems to encompass ISO 14001 and ISO 50001.
- Introduce organisational models as outlined in Legislative Decree 231/2001 and ethical codes.
- Consider SA8000 and UNI/PdR 125 to reinforce social responsibility.

b) Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation Actions

There is widespread awareness of climate change, and some specific initiatives have been undertaken, such as the installation of photovoltaic systems, the adoption of low-impact technologies, the construction of hybrid or energy-efficient vessels, and the optimisation of energy consumption. Nevertheless, these actions are often isolated and not supported by comprehensive, structured plans.

Very few companies have calculated their organisational carbon footprint or established measurable climate targets. Planning for climate change adaptation scenarios is generally absent.

Identified shortcomings:

- Fragmented and unsystematic approach.
- Absence of formalised measurements and climate objectives.

Recommendations:

- Calculate and monitor the organisational carbon footprint.
- Define and implement mitigation and adaptation plans.
- Establish clear, measurable climate-related targets.

c) ESG Sustainability

All companies demonstrated sensitivity to ESG principles, particularly with regard to ethical and social aspects, such as employees' working conditions, gender equality, transparency, and stakeholder engagement. In many cases, these values are embedded in the organisational culture but not formalised through policies, strategies, or reporting.

The measurement of ESG performance and reporting to stakeholders are generally lacking.

Identified shortcomings:

- ESG considerations are not formalised in official documents.
- Lack of performance indicators and sustainability reporting.

Recommendations:

- Formalise an ESG strategy.
- Draft a sustainability report.
- Monitor and communicate ESG performance.

d) Business Continuity

Business continuity is the least developed area. Only a minority of companies have established emergency procedures, usually limited to operational or safety incidents, and none has developed comprehensive, up-to-date business continuity plans. Awareness of operational and climate-related risks exists, but it is not translated into a long-term strategic approach.

Identified shortcomings:

- Absence of structured, tested business continuity plans.
- Limited preparedness for extreme climate events or prolonged disruptions.

Recommendations:

- Develop and periodically update business continuity plans.
- Integrate business continuity into existing management systems.
- Train personnel and test procedures on a regular basis.

Conclusions

The companies analysed demonstrate commendable levels of awareness and some tangible initiatives, albeit through a fragmented approach. The recommended actions aim to render the commitment to sustainability, climate resilience, and risk management more systematic and formalised, thereby enhancing competitiveness and alignment with international and European standards.

b) Cross-cutting Summary – GAP Analysis of some public entities connected with the Inland waterways system

SOGESCA conducted the analyses within the framework of the Horizon Europe CRISTAL project and presents the organisational positioning (GAP analysis) of the following four public entities:

- Interporto di Rovigo S.p.A.
- North Adriatic Sea Port Authority (Ports of Venice and Chioggia)
- Port of Cremona
- Port of Mantova-Valdaro

The analysis followed the methodology developed in Task 3.2 guidelines and covers the following thematic areas:

- a) Management Systems
- b) Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation Actions
- c) ESG Sustainability
- d) Business Continuity

The findings are based on structured interviews and questionnaires carried out between the second half of 2024 and the first half of 2025.

a) Management Systems

Interporto di Rovigo currently operates without certified management systems, although internal quality procedures exist. The organisation is evaluating ISO 9001 and ISO 14001 adoption to strengthen its processes and monitor environmental benefits.

North Adriatic Sea Port Authority has implemented an integrated system at the Port of Venice, certified to ISO 9001 and ISO 14001, with plans to extend these to Chioggia and introduce ISO 50001 for energy management.

Port of Cremona and **Port of Mantova-Valdaro** do not have certified management systems. Both acknowledge the potential benefits of ISO 9001 and ISO 14001 but cite constraints on staff resources and prioritisation.

Recommendations:

- Extend existing certifications and harmonise systems across port areas.
- Develop a roadmap for gradual implementation of quality, environmental, and energy management systems.
- Allocate dedicated personnel for implementation and maintenance.

b) Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation Actions

Interporto di Rovigo has implemented several emission-reduction measures (electric vehicles, LED lighting) and is progressing with cold ironing facilities. Plans include solar PV installations and participation in an energy community. Climate risk assessment and carbon footprint monitoring are recommended.

North Adriatic Sea Port Authority demonstrates good practice through its DEASP plan, OPS (cold ironing), solar PV installations, and other energy efficiency initiatives. It is aware of the impacts of sea-level rise and extreme weather and recommends further detailed risk assessments.

Port of Cremona reports challenges linked to drought-induced low river levels, sedimentation, and infrastructure limitations. Some emission-reduction initiatives (photovoltaics, heating improvements) have been realised. Further adaptation planning and risk assessment are recommended.

Port of Mantova-Valdaro is proactive in identifying risks (e.g. drought, extreme weather) and has implemented compensatory measures such as afforestation and planning for renewable energy. A structured climate risk assessment and baseline carbon footprint analysis are suggested.

Recommendations:

- Formalise climate risk assessments and develop adaptation plans.
- Establish a carbon footprint baseline and monitoring system.
- Integrate findings into strategic infrastructure planning.

c) ESG Sustainability

Interporto di Rovigo ensures worker safety, legal compliance, and has introduced welfare projects but does not publish a sustainability report.

North Adriatic Sea Port Authority publishes a Sustainability Report, informed by a materiality matrix, addressing economic, social, and environmental priorities. Further strengthening of monitoring and continuous improvement is encouraged.

Port of Cremona and **Port of Mantova-Valdaro** both highlight stakeholder engagement, compliance, and worker safety as priorities. However, neither currently reports ESG performance formally.

Recommendations:

- Formalise and communicate ESG strategy and objectives.
- Draft sustainability reports showcasing initiatives and results.
- Strengthen monitoring of environmental, social, and governance indicators.

d) Business Continuity

All four public entities exhibit awareness of potential risks to operations, particularly from geopolitical and climate-related factors. However, none has developed a formal, documented business continuity plan.

Interporto di Rovigo acknowledges global market risks and has informal procedures to maintain operations during extreme events.

North Adriatic Sea Port Authority and **Port of Mantova-Valdaro** recognise vulnerabilities, including the increasing complexity of operations due to climate impacts and infrastructure constraints.

Port of Cremona notes its dependence on river conditions and infrastructure maintenance as a key vulnerability.

Recommendations:

- Develop and formalise business continuity plans.
- Integrate continuity planning into existing management frameworks.
- Periodically test and update plans to reflect evolving risks.

Conclusion

The four ports analysed display varying levels of maturity across the thematic areas, with notable good practices (especially at Venice and Rovigo) but significant room for improvement. The recommended actions aim to enhance sustainability, resilience, and competitiveness in line with EU policy objectives.

This document provides a basis for each port to prioritise initiatives and coordinate actions towards greater organisational resilience and environmental sustainability.

5. Impact assessment of Po River Pilot solutions

The CRISTAL project aims to test and apply technologies and governance methods to make inland waterway navigation more reliable and safer.

In the context of freight and passenger transport in Italy, inland waterways account for only a residual share, even though the River Po crosses one of the most economically active areas of the country.

Inland waterway transport in Italy holds significant potential for more sustainable freight movement, particularly in terms of decarbonisation, offering a greener alternative especially to road transport of bulky and heavy goods.

The Po River has considerable transport potential, but the entire infrastructure requires modernisation and maintenance, as well as investments to improve safety and water cost management.

The main critical issues in the Italian inland waterway system are:

- **Infrastructure constraints:** the current capacity of the infrastructure limits the size and type of vessels;
- **Fleet inefficiency:** vessels are not competitive compared to those in other European countries;
- **Regulatory constraints:** the current rules on the navigability of rivers, the integration with maritime transport, and the distribution of funds hinder the efficiency and development of the sector.

The CRISTAL project addresses two of these critical issues: infrastructure constraints and regulatory constraints.

For this reason, the impact assessment of the pilot solutions must be carried out from a dual perspective: on one hand, the technological perspective, and on the other, the potential to propose solutions for reducing regulatory barriers.

A first tangible impact of the activities conducted in the pilot can already be reported and is the start of the discussion with the stakeholders and with the Italian Ministry of Infrastructure. This is an impact that cannot be measured, but it opens up many potential developments that could fully achieve the strategic objectives of the CRISTAL Project.

5.1. Objectives of the CRISTAL Project: to increase the modal share of river freight by 20% and its reliability by 80%

The strategic objectives of the CRISTAL project are to increase the modal share of river freight by 20%, increase reliability by 80%, and ensure 50% capacity during extreme events. To achieve these goals, the technologies developed provide a set of tools for real-time monitoring of infrastructure conditions, digital management of the corridors, and improved communication between managers and users.

Table 10 Technologies developed in the Italian pilot

Technology	Description/functionality	Linked CRISTAL Strategic Objectives
Fiber Optic Sensor (FOS)	FOS system is a monitoring tool used to measure the weight and the occupation volume of debris in critical section of the riverbed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase reliability by 80% • Monitoring of water depth • Enhance safety and navigability
Acoustic Emissions (AE)	Real-time detection of microcracks and structural damage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure 50% capacity during extreme events • better maintenance scheduling • Enhance safety and navigability
Digital Twin (DT)	Virtual representation of the infrastructure, allowing for simulation, analysis, and optimization of its behaviour and performance in a virtual environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the modal share of river freight by 20%, • Increase reliability by 80%, • Ensure 50% capacity during extreme events
Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)	Online platform designed to collect, consolidate and distribute current and forecast river disruption-related information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the modal share of river freight by 20% • Increase reliability by 80%
Navigability Prediction Model and Smart Bulletin	Tools (Statistical model and Machine Learning based) aimed to allow an adequate planning of the navigation activities in the river providing useful information on navigability condition in each critical section	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the modal share of river freight by 20%, • Increase reliability by 80% • Early detection and info service • Monitoring of the performances of key inland waterway assess.

Cold Ironing	Cold ironing is a shore power supply system that allows ship engines to be turned off while docked in port, without compromising the energy supply required by the vessel.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote decarbonisation and the reduction of environmental impact • Increase the modal share of river freight by 20%,
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Stakeholder of the Italian Pilot evaluation

The stakeholders' assessment of CRISTAL's expected impacts was done via a questionnaire, that considers three possible situations: business as usual scenario; Infrastructure failure scenario; Extreme weather event scenario. The questions were measured on a Lickert scale (Not at all, Slightly, Moderately; Very, Extremely). A dedicated Living Lab was made on 16th May 2025

Table 11 Validation of CRISTAL expected Impact by stakeholders

Validation Project Expected Impact These questions help validate the achievement of the strategic objectives of the CRISTAL project.	
How much such technology can help to increase the navigability of inland waterways?	Very
Can such a solution contribute to the efficient operation of the entire transport network and ensure its functionality during disruptions caused by weather or human factors?	Very
How much may the use of CRISTAL solution help to increase modal shift, including the transition to sustainable modes of transport like inland waterways and rail?	Very
How much will the use of this solution help to maintain the continuity of transport in the logistics network?	Very
Do you think this solution will make it easier to meet European legislative requirements during the construction of the infrastructure, its maintenance and use?	Moderately
How much will the governance models that will be developed allow for the development of inter-institutional, international, or inter-modal cooperation?	Moderately
Business as usual scenario - the combination of technologies (DT, SCMS, ecc.) into a single shared system	

During the normal operation of the transport network, the technologies developed in CRISTAL will collect data from the IWW infrastructure & the river/channels and make the results of the data analysis available to the SCMS and Smart Bulletin through the DT and provisional models	
To what extent will the integrated system improve operational efficiency and achieve reliability target during disruptions (weather/human factors)?	Very
Does it contribute to increasing the modal shift towards more sustainable modes of transport, such as inland waterways and railways?	Very
Will the system contribute to maintain operational continuity during disruptions across the multimodal network?	Very
Infrastructure failure scenario Sensor technologies deployed in CRISTAL that can early detect infrastructure damage (Acoustic Emissions (AE)), detect early signs of damage to an infrastructure before extensive and possible irreversible damage occurs.	
To what extent the combination of such technologies will contribute to increasing the overall navigability of inland waterway?	Very
How much will the system improve navigability during infrastructure failure events?	Very
To what extent will the use of this solution contribute to maintaining the continuity and reliability of transport operations in the logistics network?	Very
How likely is the system to facilitate compliance with EU legislation during construction, maintenance, and operation of infrastructure (e.g., will it be easier to meet the legislative requirements for maintaining the technical conditions to which hydraulic structures should comply)?	Very
Extreme weather event scenario Among the technologies produced at CRISTAL level are Fiber Optic Sensors that measure changes in water level or Acoustic Emissions that detect signs of damage to an infrastructure. These systems provide information to the SCMS and navigability prediction models to make the Smart Bulletin.	
To what extent the combination of such technologies will contribute to increasing the overall navigability of inland waterway?	Moderately

It will help to increase navigability during extreme weather events?	Moderately
Can such a solution contribute to the efficient functioning of the entire transport network and ensure its operability during disruptions caused by extreme weather conditions or human factors?	Moderately

5.2. Impacts of Smart Bulletin

All the technologies are tested in Italian river pilot under development. However, in the short term it is expected to make the smart bulletin operational. The potential benefits of the Smart Bulletin for the entire inland navigation system are listed below:

1. **Improved operational communication:** The Smart Bulletin digitises and centralises **operational communication between authorities, port operators and waterway users**, replacing the fragmentation of traditional channels (such as fax, email or phone calls).
2. **Timely decision support:** Thanks to its online interface and **real-time notification system**, it allows the **dissemination of critical alerts and updates** regarding hydrological conditions, maintenance works, malfunctions or temporary closures, thereby enhancing users' decision-making capabilities.
3. **Integrated and interoperable tool:** The Smart Bulletin is designed to **integrate with the Digital Twin** and other modules of the CRISTAL platform, forming a key component of the digital ecosystem for inland waterway corridor management.
4. **Increased operational efficiency:** By reducing the risk of **outdated or inconsistent information**, the tool helps to prevent delays, diversions or incidents, ultimately contributing to safer and more efficient navigation.
5. **User-friendly interface:** The platform offers a **simple and intuitive interface**, accessible via both desktop and mobile devices, making it suitable for users with varying levels of technical expertise.
6. **Customisable content delivery:** Users can **tailor the types of alerts they wish to receive** (e.g. low water levels, scheduled maintenance, local events), ensuring they are only notified of information relevant to their operations.
7. **Scalability and potential for wider adoption:** The Smart Bulletin can be **scaled to other regions and waterway authorities**, helping to standardise communication processes across the TEN-T corridors.

During a presentation event of the project results in Mantua, on 29th of May 2025, these benefits were illustrated to the stakeholders who confirmed the usefulness of this tool and the potential benefits to improve the reliability of inland navigation.

5.3. Governance

One of the most significant impacts of the CRISTAL project within the Italian pilot concerns governance and the effort to address long-standing management and regulatory challenges that have historically made the inland waterway sector less competitive than other transport modes.

Users and managers of the waterways have clearly outlined the key issues and necessary actions in a Manifesto (see section 4.1), which serves as a reference point for the sector's development.

From an infrastructural point of view, there is a strong need to ensure the reliable implementation of approved projects, along with the establishment of a monitoring system to oversee the condition of locks and manage riverbed maintenance through systematic dredging.

On the regulatory side, several measures have been identified as priorities. These include the creation of a more accessible support system to facilitate fleet modernisation, and the extension of the "idrobonus" incentive to cover inland navigation, which is currently excluded. There's also a call to transpose EU directives that would bring the status of inland navigation personnel in line with that of maritime workers, as well as the creation of a dedicated national employment contract for this specific sector. Furthermore, technical standards need updating to allow inland-certified vessels to operate along the coast, and local Motor Vehicle Offices require additional resources to streamline procedures and regulatory compliance.

A first step in addressing these issues was taken on 26th March 2025, when a meeting was held at the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport (MIT) to present the key findings of the Manifesto.

This was followed by a public event in Mantua in May 2025 (see chapter 5.4), which provided the opportunity to organize, following the event, a meeting between Ministry representatives and some operators. The aim was to initiate a discussion on the parameters of an incentive system that takes into account the reality of the inland navigation sector, which is made up of companies that typically operate on a smaller scale than their maritime counterparts, both in terms of volumes and turnover, and therefore require targeted support measures.

5.4. Italian Pilot final event

The waterway system in Italy is relatively small compared to other EU countries, but it offers good potential for development¹². However, it needs to be better known by highlighting ongoing projects aimed at enhancing its usability, reliability, and sustainability, such as the CRISTAL Project.

It was therefore deemed important to organize a public event in Mantua on 29th May 2025 (Figure 38) to present the project and the results of the Italian pilot, also involving the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport.

Moreover, this event represented the final phase of the Living Lab cycle, with the presentation of the results of the contributions received in the living labs.

¹² See D 7.1, chapter 2.3 and chapter 2.5

After the presentation from the Italian partners of the Project of the main solutions and systems developed in CRISTAL and implemented in the pilot, even if at different level, the IWW institutions and stakeholders, such as the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport, the Veneto Region, Intesa Interregionale per la Navigazione Interna sul fiume Po”, the province of Mantua, Fondazione ITL Autostrada del Brennero and Quadrante Europa, participated in a round table on the future of the Italian waterway as an infrastructure for freight and passenger transport.

In this section, many points were highlighted such as:

- The need to increase the visibility of inland waterways as a possible solution for freight and passenger transport;
- The fundamental contribution of technological innovation in making inland waterways more competitive and resilient;
- The importance of networking inland waterways with other transport infrastructure (roads and railways) using a co-opetition approach to maximize the benefits for users of these infrastructures.

It is important to underline that the work carried out in the CRISTAL project can offer an answer to many of the points mentioned above, demonstrating the value of the results achieved.

Finally, all speakers emphasized that cooperation between stakeholders at various levels is an enabling factor for the development of the Italian waterway system, and commitments were made to strengthen this collaboration.

Progetto CRISTAL

Una visione strategica per lo sviluppo sostenibile del Sistema Idroviario Padano-Veneto

29 MAGGIO 2025

MANTOVA

Palazzo del Plenipotenziario, Piazza Sordello 43

9.30 REGISTRAZIONE PARTECIPANTI Modera Andrea Ballarin

10.00 SALUTI E INTRODUZIONE

Salvatore Napoli, Direttore Generale per i porti, la logistica e l'intermodalità, MIT
 Alessandra Grosso, Direttore Generale, Infrastrutture Venete
 Gianluca Zanichelli, Direttore Generale, AIPo
 Alessio Picarelli, Dirigente Servizio navigazione Interna, AIPo

10.30 PRESENTAZIONE DEL PROGETTO PILOTA ITALIANO

Luca Zanetta, Responsabile progetti europei, Uniontrasporti
 Luca Crose, Progetti europei, navigazione, ricerca tecnico-Scientifica, AIPo
 Riccardo Maratini, Consulente di Infrastrutture Venete

11.40 CONSULTAZIONE E CONCERTAZIONE: IL MANIFESTO DEL SISTEMA IDROVIARIO

Rose Ortolani, Project manager ambiente ed energia, SOGESCA

12.00 UNA VISIONE STRATEGICA DELLO SVILUPPO DEL SISTEMA IDROVIARIO: SOSTENIBILITÀ, INTEGRAZIONE E COMPLEMENTARITÀ
Intervengono

Luca Pentrella, Direzione Generale per i porti, la logistica e l'intermodalità, MIT
 Andrea Menin, Direttore dell'UO logistica, navigazione, ispettorati di porto e pianificazione, Regione Veneto
 Delegato Intesa Interregionale per la navigazione interna sul fiume Po
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13.00 CONCLUSIONI

Progetto CRISTAL

Una visione strategica per lo sviluppo sostenibile del Sistema Idroviario Padano-Veneto

Palazzo del Plenipotenziario, Piazza Sordello 43

29 maggio 2025

Figure 38 Italian pilot final event – agenda and save the date
 Source: Own elaboration

The event was attended by over 40 people representing institutions, associations, private and public companies, demonstrating the existence of a high level of interest in technologies, solutions and governance models that can contribute to the development of the waterway.

5.5. Potential impact of the technologies: KPIs

The following KPIs refer only to the specific solutions of the Italian pilot project.

For each of these KPIs, the value was measured (or set up) before the before implementation of the solution to which it refers (baseline value) and then measured (or estimated) after the implementation of the solution (final value).

Given a KPI, the comparison between its two values provides an indication of the benefit provided by the solution under consideration.

The final value of all KPIs has been calculated except for two of the three KPIs related to the smart bulletin which will be reported in the deliverable D7.3

Table 12 Italian pilot KPIs for the technology/system developed in WP7

Technology	KPIs	How the KPI will be measured	Measuring data	Base line	Final
Cold ironing	ENV4-NOX (tonnes)	Estimated	Data referred to emissions while mooring in the Fissero-Tartaro-CanalBianco waterway	11 tonnes	0,25 tonnes
Cold ironing	ENV5-PM (kg)	Estimated	Data referred to emissions while mooring in the Fissero-Tartaro-CanalBianco waterway	233 kg	7 kg
Cold ironing	ENV6-GHG as CO ₂ e (tonnes of CO ₂)	Estimated	Data referred to emissions while mooring in the Fissero-Tartaro-CanalBianco waterway	500 tonnes of CO ₂	130 tonnes of CO ₂
Cold ironing	ENV7-Energy consumption (toe)	Estimated	Data referred to energy consumption while mooring in the Fissero-Tartaro-CanalBianco waterway	60 toe	45 toe
Living Labs - cycle governance	(S1) Number of new or adjusted: - governance models (i.e. governance Manifesto)	Measured	Through the Living Lab, a long-term agreement with all the waterway stakeholders will be set up and the foundations will be laid for a more cohesive and consistent governance framework	0	1
Forecast model	- solutions (i.e. smart bulletin) - roadmaps and guidelines (i.e. implementation plan)	Measured	The output of the navigability conditions models will be presented in a new smart bulletin	0	1
Cold ironing		Measured	The cold ironing feasibility study will develop the implementation plan	0	1
Forecast model	(ITA 4) Navigation forecast points along the river	Test	Number of forecast points	0	132

Smart bulletin	Social acceptance survey results (Likert scale)	Measured	Questionary/Tests in a LL (o event)	Not applicable	Q1: 4.06 Q2: 3,35 ¹³
Smart bulletin	Smart bulletin downloads	Measured (SB field test)	Counter on AIPo web site/service	20	Still to be calculated (results in D7.3)
Smart bulletin	Registered users	Measured (SB field test)	Nr. of subscriptions (on AIPo platform)	15	Still to be calculated (results in D7.3)

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Mantua: 29 May 2025 QUESTION	ANSWERS					KPI Linker scale
	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely	
Q1: Do you think a +10-day forecast smart bulletin improves planning capacity in freight or passenger transport?	0%	6%	13%	50%	31%	4.06
Q2: Do you think the information contained is sufficient or should it be supplemented with additional information?	5%	12%	24%	59%	0%	3.35

6. Conclusions

This document collects the results of the development and testing activities carried out in the Italian pilot project.

The Italian pilot is significant for the involvement of a wide range of stakeholders, reflecting the complexity of a system that includes various infrastructure managers, authorities, and types of operators.

The maintenance and development of inland waterways and their associated infrastructure (such as docks, locks, etc.) are essential components, supported by both public and private initiatives. The overall aim is to ensure the functionality and safety of navigation.

Although not extensively used for large-scale commercial freight, inland waterways are primarily employed for tourism and local transport. When it comes to freight transport, this mode is mostly used for the movement of bulky and heavy goods.

However, the lack of suitable infrastructure that would enable better integration with other transport modes—particularly rail—and certain structural limitations currently make inland navigation a less appealing option within the broader national freight transport system.

For this reason, one of the stakeholders' main priorities is to have tools that can enhance the reliability and visibility of this transport mode.

Technological applications such as the FOS, Digital Twin (DT), and AE are intended to create an integrated and interoperable system for the collection of data, which is crucial for real-time monitoring of infrastructure conditions—both under normal circumstances and in response to extreme weather events or human actions that may disrupt navigation. Through tools like the SCMS and the Smart Bulletin, businesses will be able to plan their activities and redirect traffic in the event of problems, ensuring that agreements with clients are honoured within the necessary timeframes. Governance models, meanwhile, are aimed at resolving regulatory issues and fostering ongoing cooperation among the various parties involved.

The potential and objectives of the project were shared with stakeholders during Living Labs and events showcasing the main results.

Future developments will depend, among other things, on:

- the availability of financial resources to invest in technology;
- economic incentives for fleet renewal;
- the implementation of the “Idrobonus” scheme;
- regulatory updates to make inland navigation more competitive compared to other modes of transport.

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